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Antecedents and Outcomes of Volunteering at Workplace

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine the factors that lead to and influence workplace volunteering in Pakistan's mobile telecommunications sector. Research on volunteering has been limited, thus we picked Job design (individual autonomy in working decisions and procedures) and personality traits (five-factor personality) for the antecedents and job performance as results. The data is collected through structured questionnaires from 340 employees who worked in the Telecom sector. SPSS is used for statistical analysis. In our study, we discovered a strong correlation between the antecedents and outcomes of workplace volunteering. A unique aspect of the study is that it examined job design in terms of individual autonomy in making working decisions and working procedures as a precursor to individual volunteering. Our findings will help the enterprises to get their employees involved in volunteering, as well as boost their employees' ability to build a positive social image of their organizations.

Keywords: Antecedents of volunteering, outcome of volunteering, job design, personality traits, company level factors, work method autonomy, work decision autonomy, extraversion, conscientiousness, neuroticism, open to experience, agreeableness, employees volunteering, corporate volunteering

Introduction:

The current business environment requires firms to be financially stable and socially responsible, both of which are important in today's business climate (Rodell, 2017). In order to achieve this goal, organizations must implement "corporate volunteering programs," which are a collection of official and informal techniques and practices aimed at encouraging employees to volunteer in their places of employment (Li et al., 2013; Rodell, 2013). Individual volunteering research has increased substantially in recent years, notably in the context of workplace characteristics and psychological outcomes (e.g., Rodell, 2017, 2015 & 2013; Musick & Wilson, 2007; Grant, 2012). Scholarly research on volunteering has conclusively demonstrated that employee volunteering

benefits both firms and people. Volunteering is "unpaid work performed to parties to whom the worker owes no contractual, familial, or friendship obligations," according to Wilson & Musick (1997) (quoted in Tilly & Tilly, 1994).

The definition of employee volunteering is consistent with Rodell (2015) by adhering to the organizational behavior and motivations underlying volunteering behavior in the workplace and is defined as "*Employed individuals giving time during a planned activity for an external nonprofit or charitable organization.*" Furthermore, studies on volunteering explore that companies achieve competitive edge when the design and initiate employees volunteering with objectives to attain the motives of volunteers. A report (2024) by Deloitte shows same type of notion by describing the fact that 87% of employees perform workplace volunteering with their intention to stay within organization, and 91% perform because they are interested to increase their work experience and connection with peers (Deloitte, 2024). Similarly, Li and Chen (2025) reported that corporate volunteering is positively associated with job performance and satisfaction. Their findings support the idea that corporate volunteering frameworks followed by motives volunteering (e.g., values, career, social functions) are important and relevant and must be align with the employees values and skills, and their meaningful participation, so that employees can achieve intrinsic satisfaction.

Previous research on volunteering has looked at why people want to help their communities by volunteering (Wilson & Musick, 1997; Lee, Brudeny, 2015). Volunteering is a unique part of life that can be seen from different points of view. We call this a "domain." People are becoming more interested in this area of action because they can tell it apart from other things they've done and because they want to do something "meaningful." Volunteering is one way people can find meaning, which supports the idea that work can be a source of meaning (e.g. Hackman & Oldham, 1980; Rosso, Dekas, & Wrzesniewski, 2010). In academic research on employee volunteering, different combinations of individual motivations and results have also been looked at (Booth et al., 2009; Grant, 2012; Rodell et al; 2015).

The research followed the scholarly model of corporate volunteering by Rodell et al. (2017), which intertwines supported and unsupported ties at both the organizational and person level. The concept of "Corporate Volunteering Climate" is driven by two types of processes: employee-driven processes (led by beliefs and convictions) and company-driven processes (e.g., resources and benefits). These two types of processes come about when employees interact with each other. Before putting their actions into a meaningful context, people in this process wait for information and social cues. Furthermore, it is also discovered from the cognitive assessment hypothesis (Deci, 1975) says that a person's motivation is affected from the inside by what happens outside of them. According to the cognitive evaluation theory, there are two types of motivation: internal and extrinsic. Internal motivation comes from achievement, accountability, and competence (Pay, promotion, feedback and working conditions).

This article is one of the few to present a comprehensive investigation of the antecedents of workplace volunteering, including an in-depth analysis of personality factors and a job design perspective. Second, a novel aspect of our study is analyzing job performance as an employee-level outcome of volunteering. Our findings would also have practical implications for enterprises, since managers would be able to ensure that

their staff have access to volunteer opportunities. Furthermore, we provide a summary of the present literature on corporate volunteering, whereas our discussion recommends innovative future study possibilities.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development:

In recent years, corporate volunteering has become a growing trend in voluntary action (Wilson, 2012) because it allows employees to combine volunteering with their jobs (Haski-Leventhal, Meijs, & Hustinx, 2010). Employers support and create CV programs to encourage employees to do volunteer work outside of the company (Kotler & Lee, 2005). These programs let employees use their knowledge and/or skills to help the community while they are at work as part of the employer's community service, outreach, or social responsibility activity (de Gilder, Schuyt, & Breedijk, 2005). CV helps a lot of nonprofit organizations (NPOs), but it also helps for-profit companies and employees, especially when it comes to employee engagement and good results at work. Volunteering can make people feel like they have a purpose and a sense of meaning at work (Rodell, 2013), which can indirectly boost affective commitment and job satisfaction. CV has the potential to make employees more emotionally committed to a company by changing how they see themselves and the company (Grant, Dutton, & Rosso, 2008).

From an organizational standpoint, motives may provide a more useful basis for involving and addressing employee volunteering issues in firms (Clary et al., 1999). Both qualitative and quantitative research has shown that volunteers typically have various reasons and are ambitious (Pajo & Lee, 2011; Peloza & Hassay, 2006). As a result, researchers have created and implemented a number of models to track the reasons why people volunteer (Clary et al., 1998; Omoto & Snyder, 1995).

The values function shows values that are based on the idea that helping other people is important. Understanding is defined as "the ability to learn new things and use skills, knowledge, and abilities." Batson's four motive theory from 2002 says that there are four types of reasons why people volunteer: egoism (to improve one's own welfare, such as happiness, social recognition, praise, and avoiding guilt), altruism (to improve the welfare of others, such as through empathy and compassion), collectivism (to improve the welfare of groups, such as through Humanity Cause), and principles (to improve the welfare of individuals) (Motivation is to uphold some moral principle).

There is a growing body of research that shows a positive link between volunteering and positive workplace attitudes (e.g., de Gilder et al., 2005; Peterson, 2004; Plewa, Conduit, Quester, & Johnson, 2015). However, we still don't know enough about how organizations organize volunteering programs and what motivates employees to take part in these activities, which are part of the process and lead to these results.

Antecedents of Volunteering at the Workplace

Personality Traits and Volunteering:

A personality trait is a tendency to act in a certain way no matter what is going on. For example, a character trait is a pattern of behavior such as being friendly, that shows up in different social situations and relationships and stays the same over time (Penner et al. 2005). Because volunteering is an activity that people do on their own time, personality differences may play a role in who volunteers.

Personality psychologists take a glance at the "big five" traits—extroversion, neuroticism, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness to experience—for clues about how to help people (Krause, N., & Rainville, 2018). Extroversion means not being shy around other people, being assertive and sure of yourself, and having a high energy level. Neuroticism is the tendency to see the world as upsetting or dangerous, a low sense of self-efficacy, and a weak sense of mastery. People who are careful and careful about what they do are conscientious. Agreeableness is the trait of being helpful, kind, considerate, empathetic, generous, trustworthy, and cooperative. Openness to experience is "the most debated and least understood of the big five trends." It means that people tend to look for stimulation and explore new environments, being creative, sensitive to art, and wise. Volunteers are likely to do well on extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness. Coffee, on the other hand, is likely to do well on neuroticism.

Furthermore, according to the cognitive evaluation theory, both intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence people's decision to take certain activities. For instance, a person with a strong feeling of altruism could volunteer at work in order to get internal advantages. As the previous studies demonstrated, voluntary employees represent an organization's social human capital and offer numerous advantages by enhancing organizational culture, fostering employee engagement, boosting job satisfaction, and boosting productivity. Therefore, it is crucial for businesses to value volunteerism in their staff members as well as to recognize the specific personality features that enable them to spot new hires who share those attributes and improve each employee's motivational experience. So, using the five-factor model of personality traits, we have created the hypothesis to evaluate personality traits in this context.

H1: There exists a positive relationship between extraversion and individual volunteering at the workplace

H2: There exists a positive relationship between conscientiousness and individual volunteering at the workplace

H3: There exists a positive relationship between openness to experience and individual volunteering at the workplace

H4: There exists a positive relationship between neuroticism and individual volunteering at the workplace

H5: There exists a positive relationship between agreeableness and individual volunteering at the workplace

Job Design and Volunteering:

Recent research into the motivations of German Wikipedia volunteers has shed light on the potential significance of job design hypotheses for volunteer work (Schroer and Hertel, 2009). In their study, researchers found that volunteer contributors' commitment and satisfaction were shaped by their perceptions of task characteristics (autonomy, skill variety, task significance, and feedback). Findings from previous studies using this framework motivated our investigation of intrinsic motivation and its relationship to increased self-determination. Research has shown, for example, that controlling rewards (Hao et al., 2018), deadlines (Amabile et al., 2018), and evaluations (Amabile, 2018) can reduce the gratification of doings, whereas choice (Zuckerman et al., 1978) and acknowledging an individual's spirits toward accomplishments or guidelines regarding an activity (Milyavskaya et. al., 2011) can enhance it. The job design literature, on the other hand, provides a viable framework for theorizing, examining, and assessing the task-related characteristics and motivational functions of intra-organizational volunteer programs.

Furthermore, according to Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000), individuals have basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Perspectives that provide for the satisfaction of these needs will encourage an individual's action satisfaction and autonomous behavior. Individuals are more likely to be intrinsically motivated, that is, to do an activity simply for the pleasure of it, when they have the freedom to pursue the activity (autonomy), when they master the activity (competence), and when they feel connected to and supported by managers at work. Previous findings in this context inspired the facts for examining how an increase in experienced autonomy influenced intrinsic motivation. Controlling rewards (Deci, 1971), deadlines (Amabile et al., 2018), and evaluation (Amabile, 2018), for example, have been shown in studies to decrease the gratification of doings, whereas choice (Zuckerman et al., 1978) and acknowledging individual spirits toward accomplishments or guidelines regarding an activity (Gagné, M, 2003) can enrich it. Thus, using the classic Job design model and self-determination theory, we can see that autonomy in terms of individual volunteering at work is an important aspect of research. Thus, the following hypothesis is developed,

H6: *There is a positive relationship between Work Decision Autonomy and Individual Volunteering.*

H7: *There is a positive relationship between Work Methods Autonomy and Individual Volunteering.*

Job Performance: Outcome of Volunteering at the workplace:

According to the theory of planned behavior, a person's actions are affected and shaped by how they feel about and why they want to do certain things. Previous research has shown that the volunteers are very interested in learning new skills and want to get ready for careers. Individual attitudes that start and keep the behavior going are based on behavioral beliefs. This means that motivations are the most important factor in determining attitudes (Cho, Bonn, and Han, 2018). When the role of motivations is applied to volunteering, motivations for volunteering could also make people like certain interests more. Broad S.(2003) found that as volunteers develop deeper motivations because of their social and intrinsic motivations, they also develop more positive attitudes that make them even happier with volunteering and help them do a better job. For example, the CSR Congruence Model (Haski-Leventhal, Roza, & Meijs, 2017) says that when employees' and employers' socially responsible actions (like taking part in CV) and identities (like having positive CSR attitudes) are in line, good things can happen, like employee engagement, job satisfaction, and commitment.

Researchers have also found that people who are highly motivated to volunteer are happier than those who are not as motivated. For instance, in his speech to the Society of Alcoholism in 1982, Wilson said that volunteering gives the volunteer a chance to be "Self-Actualized." This is a term that Abraham Maslow used in his theory of the hierarchy of needs. So, workers with a high level of self-actualization are more productive than workers with a low level of self-actualization. In the previous study, most of the scholars who talked about why people volunteer talked about "meaningfulness" (Clary et al., 1999). Volunteering as a way to find meaning backs up the idea that a job can be a source of meaning (e.g. Hackman & Oldham, 1980; Rosso, Dekas, & Wrzesniewski, 2010).

According to the cognitive evaluation theory (Deci, 1975), external consequences influence internal motivation. Thus, there are two motivational mechanisms: intrinsic (achievement, responsibility, and competence) and extrinsic (rewards and recognition) (Pay, promotion, feedback and working conditions). According to the theory,

persons who are intrinsically motivated have an internal locus of causation. Thus, the persons who volunteer at work are intrinsically driven and relate their conduct to internal demands for intrinsic rewards and satisfaction, as well as the desire to improve their job performance. Thus, we have considered job performance as the result of volunteering in the workplace; this is yet another novelty of our study. Therefore, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H8: There exist a positive relationship between Job performance and individual volunteering

(Research Model)

Independent Variable: Job Design (*Work Decision Autonomy, Work Method Autonomy*), Personality Traits (*Extraversion, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, Open to experience, Agreeableness*)

Dependent Variable: Individual Volunteering, Job Performance

Research Methodology

Data Collection and Sampling:

To conduct this study, a structured questionnaire was used to gather primary data. 340 telecom employees from Ufone, Mobilink, Telenor, and ZONG provided data on their individual volunteerism. The survey data is analysed with SPSS software. Random sampling and structured surveys are used to gather information. Employees of telecom companies such as Mobilink, Telenor, Ufone, and Zong were used as the sampling unit for a questionnaire. In order to better understand the reasons why people volunteer and how it affects their job performance, a questionnaire was developed. The information was gathered by distributing questionnaires to

employees in the HR departments of the telecom companies in order to get information from them. Human resources professionals were urged to distribute questionnaires at random to workers. Individual Volunteering, Personality Traits, Job Design, Company Level Factors, and Job Performance were all included in the questionnaire.

From November 15th to December 5th, 2018, four telecom companies participated in a poll. Mobilink, Ufone, Telenor, and Zong each received 100 questionnaires, which were then distributed evenly among the four companies. Out of the 400 surveys, 340 were fully completed, representing an overall response rate of 85%. All responders have been informed that the data and information they provide will only be used for research purposes and will be kept private.

Operationalization of Variables:

To operationalize the variables, multiple measures were applied in the study as presented in the conceptual model of this study. Three items (Individual Volunteering (IV), Personality Traits (PST) & Job Performance (JP)) were rated using five point Likert scale, ranging from 5 (Strongly Agree) to 1 (Strong Disagree). Two items Job Design (JD) and Company level factors (C.F)) were rated using binary rating, ranging from 0 (NO), and 1 (YES). The demographic information of the respondents i.e. Gender, Age, Qualification, Job level and work experience were recorded by using open ended questions. Age, Work Experience and Job level were coded in SPSS on 4 scales; Qualification on 5 scales and Gender were coded as binary variable 1=Male, 0=Female.

The questionnaire for Individual Volunteering was designed to find out how much volunteering each person does. A five-point Likert scale has been used, with 5 being "Strongly Agree" and 1 being "Strongly Disagree." This questionnaire asked seven questions. I.e., I'm very interested in volunteering, I spend money on volunteering, I belong to a society or club for volunteers, volunteering is a top priority in my life, I spend time on volunteering activities, I'm happy to volunteer, and I look for opportunities to volunteer. The independent variable is the personality trait variable. The Big Five John Questionnaire, made by John and Srivastava, is used to measure personality traits (1999). This questionnaire used 44 questions to measure the "big five" personality traits: agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, openness to experience, and extraversion. The questionnaire uses the Five-Point Likert Scale, which goes from 5 (Strongly Agree) to 1 (Strongly Disagree) (Strongly Disagree). As an independent variable, the job design is used. Work Schedule Autonomy (WSA), Work Decision Autonomy (WDA), and Work Method Autonomy (WMA), which were taken from a scale used by P.Morgeson and E. Humphrey, were the items for Job Design Indicators (2006). Each person asked themselves nine questions to figure out how much freedom they had at work. The scale also has two-digit values (0, 1). The independent variable is the job performance variable. Four items from Williams & Anderson were used to measure job performance (1991). Four questions were asked to figure out how well the person did their job. In this section, you had to answer questions about how well you did your assigned tasks, how well you met the responsibilities listed in the job description, how well you did the expected tasks, and how well you met the formal performance requirements of the job. Five Likert scales were used to measure how people felt, with 5 being "Strongly Agree" and 1 being "Strongly Disagree" (Strongly Disagree).

Results:

Table#1 shows model summary of measuring Personality Traits (Five factor personality traits) as an independent variable and individual volunteering (I.V) as dependent variable. The value of adjusted- R-square is .652. Which shows that model is acceptable and have high effect size.

(Table: 1)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.810 ^a	.657	.652	.85820

Five hypotheses under personality traits are develop to measure their relationship with individual volunteering. i.e.

- H1:** *There exist a positive relationship between extraversion and individual volunteering.*
- H2:** *There exist a positive relationship between conscientiousness and individual volunteering.*
- H3:** *There exist a positive relationship between neuroticism and individual volunteering.*
- H4:** *There exist a positive relationship between open to experience and individual volunteering.*
- H5:** *There exist a positive relationship between agreeableness and individual volunteering.*

(Table: 2)

Coefficients^a					
	B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
Extraversion	.599	.162	.351	3.691	.000
Conscientiousness	.427	.132	.211	3.228	.001
Neuroticism	.011	.060	.007	.176	.861
Open to Experience	.601	.122	.445	4.931	.000
Agreeableness	.289	.109	.182	2.663	.008

a. *Dependent Variable: Individual Volunteering*

Extraversion (H3, $p < 0.05$, $t=3.691$), Conscientiousness (H4, $p < 0.0$, $t=3.3228$), Open to experience (H6, $p < 0.05$, $t=4.931$) and Agreeableness (H7, $p < 0.05$, $t=2.663$) are positively related to individual volunteering and significant. But neuroticism (H3, $p > 0.05$, $t=.176$) is insignificant and not supported.

There are Two Hypothesis develop to measure Job design effect on Individual Volunteering. i.e.

H6: There's exist a Positive relationship between Work Decision Autonomy (WDA) and Individual Volunteering.
H7: There's exist a Positive relationship between Work Method Autonomy (WMA) and individual volunteering.
 The Table (4) shows that Work Design Autonomy (**H1**, p value < 0.05) and Work Method Autonomy (**H2**, p value < 0.05) are significant to dependent variable individual volunteering. Where t value is also showing positive significant relationship i.e. (WDA (t= 3.022), WMA (t=4.049)). Thus both hypothesis are significant and supported with their results.

(Table: 3)

Coefficients ^a					
	B	Std. Error	Standardized Beta	T3	Sig.
WorkDecision Autonomy	1.026	.340	.276	3.022	.003
WorkMethod Autonomy	1.228	.303	.370	4.049	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Individual Volunteering

H8: There's exist a positive relationship between Job performance and individual volunteering.
 Below Table shows that Job performance (H8, P < 0.05, t=12.278) is highly significant and supported.

(Table: 4)

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Job Performance	.506	.041	.555	12.278	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Individual Volunteering

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Overall, the present study has provided significant answers to all research questions. Job design and personality traits have significant relations with the individual volunteering. Also individual volunteering has strong significant impact on the job performance of the employees. The study found that work decision autonomy and work method autonomy has significant relationship with individual volunteering and also out of five personality factors, extraversion, conscientiousness, open to experience, and agreeableness has significant relationship with individual volunteering while neuroticism does not support the relationship with individual volunteering and insignificant.

Our study identify the positive relationship between Job design and volunteering by discussing the two inner perspectives of job design i.e. work decision autonomy and work method autonomy as the two effective antecedents for employees volunteering at work place. That's support by job design theory in the paid employment context. Job design theory states that,

"When jobs are designed to provide incumbents with an opportunity for them to perceive positive impact on beneficiaries, they invest more time and energy into their tasks".

Also, Grant (2012) found that work context facilitating volunteering includes, work schedules, payment schedules, and job uncertainty. These all aspects of work determines employees temporarily and financial autonomy. Elsbach & Hargadon (2018) study found that job designs tend to free up time, energy, and activities at work. Most of research has discuss social and knowledge characteristics of work but a very few research has been discussed in order to autonomy perspectives of Job design. According to self-determination theory, autonomy orientation is strongly related to engagement in prosaically behavior i.e. volunteering (Rodell., 2015). Thus, our findings extend the existing literature of job design by studying the "work decisional autonomy" and "work methods autonomy".

Further, Results of our study has accepted the hypothesis regarding extraversion, consciousness, open to experiences and agreeableness. It means that employees who has positively personality traits related to extraversion, consciousness, open to experience and agreeableness tends to more involved in volunteering activities. It is also confirm by Graziano and Eisenberg (1977) that agreeableness is strongly contributing towards prosaically behaviors. And similarly extraversion is positively related to social ability, positive emotions and warmth activity (Carlo et al., 2005). Our findings are also consistent with the findings of Jabri et al., (2012) that's found positive relationship of extraversion, consciousness, open to experience and agreeableness with volunteering satisfaction and neuroticism as a negatively related as well.

In the organizational perspectives, five factor personality traits differentiate individuals from one another by their personality traits and motives. Thus our results are more important and specific in the organizational perceptive at workplace. The trait of "neuroticism" is found insignificant with our results. The historical evidence regarding "neuroticism" has negative or low level relationship with volunteering because it contras with the idea of "altruistic" behavior (e.g. Grant, 2012). One of other reason may be that response from the respondents may be similar or high, so that it has be shown insignificant. We have also found strong significant relationship between the Job performance and individual volunteering at workplace. That's inconsistent with findings Rodell (2013) that volunteering is associated with job meaningfulness that's result in better job performance. But our study is different from Rodell (2013) study because it revealed the facts by considering the variables i.e. compensation, enhancement and resource drain yet our findings based on factors i.e. job design autonomy and personality traits. Thus our study is producing another view of volunteering impacts on employee's job performance. Because our study adding values by replying the oldest and un-answered question i.e. how does volunteering impact work related outcome? (Rodell, 2017). Thus, it is also being noted that our study is initial research who founds the direct positive and significant relationship of volunteering at work place and job performance.

Limitations of the Study:

In this study we have identify the antecedents and outcomes of individual volunteering at workplace by considering company level factors as a moderating variable. However, there are some limitations of this research. The data has been collected in this research is through cross sectional approach that concerns about the generalizability of our research. Moreover, we have ignored the gender factors i.e. male's rates of volunteering verses female's rates of volunteering.

Further, we have chosen job design autonomy from two perspectives. But others perspectives can also be important like social characteristic of job design, Task characteristics and autonomy of jobs by position level. In findings our results, we only consider WDA and WMA as a positive impact for volunteering and ultimate impact on job performance. But negative factors can also be created by autonomy like non-serious attitude, inadequate job performance etc.

Future Research

Future studies regarding antecedents and outcomes of individual volunteering should explore the new aspects of antecedents and outcomes. To understand antecedents of volunteering more deeply, focus group, longitudinal, and experimental studies will be more authentic and generalizable in their results.

Moreover, future research can also be conducted on different work context and also on organizational climate towards volunteering. For example, diversity and volunteering, designations level of employees, experience and promotions perspectives.

Corporate volunteering is a new emerging concept and has lot of potential by establishing mutual relationship b/w employee and employers. Yet, a lot of literature has discussed the motives regarding individual but motives regarding employers remains indistinct, thus future research is invited in order to conduct studies regarding motives of organizational perspectives.

Moreover, in developed countries, volunteering programs are utilized to fight with grand challenges i.e. Hunger, Poverty, Education or Health cause. In developing countries, these issues can be resolved by initiating corporate volunteering programs for these concern, thus, future research can also be conduct to develop models for corporate volunteering programs to challenge grand issues.

Conclusion

In this study we have identify the antecedents and outcomes of volunteering at workplace by taking mobile telecom sectors as a case study. The study concluded that job design and personality traits are the important antecedents for employees who perform volunteer activities. The novelty of our research is that we have taken variable i.e. Work Decision Autonomy (WDA) and Work Method Autonomy (WMA) have never been used in previous research and extends the existing literature of Job design with perspectives of volunteering. Moreover, we have found direct outcome of volunteering activities at workplace by choosing "Job Performance" as an outcome. Our findings would also have practical implications for enterprises, since managers would be able to ensure that their staff has access to volunteer opportunities.

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